

IMPACT OF THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION ON THE GROWTH OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The study entitled impact of the industrial revolution on the growth of management education in India. The quality of the education provided by these management colleges and whether the M.B.A. graduates have gained the requisite skill set to be marketable in the job market are of paramount importance to all stakeholders. There have been stories of M.B.A. graduates having difficulty finding work in the global labor market. As a result, improving the quality of higher education is a top priority. Because of this, it is necessary to conduct a student satisfaction survey for NBA-accredited students in Tamil Nadu. A qualitative research design is employed in this study. Academic specialists provided the critical data for this study. This study relied on secondary data. Secondary sources included academic journals, theses, magazines, and other periodicals.

Keywords: Job Market, Industrial Economic Growth, Industrial Revolution, Institutional Infrastructure, Management Education.

INTRODUCTION OF THE STUDY

A recent development in higher education has been the proliferation of Management Institutions, students, and professors. Tamil Nadu State is no exception to this extraordinary growth in management education. A variety of specialized and super-specialized fields of study have developed to meet the ever-changing demands of the marketplace and the public safety community alike. These include marketing and sales, facilities and disaster relief and crisis management, and fields like information technology (I.T.) and project management (project management). Managerial skills and capacities are at the heart of management education, aiming to prepare future workforces to meet global demands. Executive education has been mostly restricted to those who work in the private sector rather than recognizing that management skills are needed in all sectors of society. It is generally confined to the needs of industry and business.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Educational advancement has a tremendous impact on national economic growth, according to Malos Raul Cezar and his co-authors. After that, we develop an economic growth model

that incorporates more and more processes. We looked at a few variables to demonstrate the link between human capital and economic growth. Many other mathematical models have been developed using 1990-2006 data to examine the relationship between the I.B.P. and the previous year's level and many influencing variables that can be used to gauge the importance of education in building human capital.

Students' expectations and impressions of the quality of their educational experience and the academic standards of their chosen programs of study were examined in 2012-13 by Kandiko, C.B., and Mawer, M. (2013) in higher education across the U.K. In the first year of a new funding arrangement in England, students' expectations and perceptions of quality and bars were examined in the study. It is vastly different from what was in place in the U.K. in the past and what was in place in the rest of the world.

According to Murali, engineering graduates in India are expected to meet corporate expectations. S. and Y. Rajaram (2015). A person's five most essential resources are Entrepreneurship, Material, Methods, Money, and Human Resources. Human resources stand out because they are living things; they are the glue that holds the rest of the team together since, without them, the others cease to exist. It's no longer only about planning, sustaining, managing, and monitoring; human resources are now actively contributing to the core of businesses through Human resource audits. Human resources are currently on an entirely new level. Human resources have undergone a sea change because of this. Human resource managers have a significant impact on an organization's strategic planning by bringing in new skill sets, providing accurate forecasts, and ensuring that the organization's human resource requirements are met. They significantly impact the organization's ability to recruit, train, and retain new and experienced employees. Engineering graduates in India are examined in this study, which focuses on business expectations.

On sustainable banking, Ijeoma Nwagwu (2020) focuses on how business schools and management development institutes may promote responsible management education to meet the Sustainable Development Goals (S.D.G.s). In Nigeria, a developing country in sub-Saharan Africa, the article explores the role of business schools and management development institutes in increasing progress toward achieving the S.D.G.s. Globalized banking and financial sectors have yet to fully utilize the prospects for sustainable growth because of a lack of a clear understanding of incorporating sustainability in banking systems. It is examined in this context. Recommendations for accelerating S.D.G. achievement through sustainable banking are offered considering ongoing systemic efforts, including responsible management education.

A network slacks-based measure (S.B.M.) model was used to evaluate the efficiency of the process, and then an individual fixed effect model was used to analyze it. Xuejie Bai et al. (2020) divided the process through which China's higher education investment turned into industrial economic growth between 2014 and 2017. Between 2014 and 2017, China's investment in higher education yielded industrial economic growth, as detailed in this study. Higher education investment transformation, knowledge innovation, and commercialization are the three main components. The slacks-Based Measure (S.B.M.) model is then used to

assess the process' efficiency. Finally, the individual fixed-effect model examines the model's affecting parts.

Glaucoma, A study by Gomes Soares et al. (2021) examined the effect of corporate entrepreneurship education on the long-term viability of small family businesses. When compared to other types of enterprises, family-owned companies have significant advantages. More research is needed for family businesses to thrive and last in today's global economy. Corporate entrepreneurship education is still necessary for family firms, despite their prominence. According to this research, corporate entrepreneurship education in Brazil has improved competitiveness, ensured sustainability, and aided in the smooth transition of a company's leadership from one generation to the next. We used an exploratory-descriptive approach that relied on qualitative data and discourse analysis for the study. Interviews with the family firm's top management were used to gain data on how they regarded corporate entrepreneurship education. According to the findings, the company is a typical family business. To safeguard the company's long-term viability and smooth leadership transition, the company invested in corporate entrepreneurship education. Investing in education for corporate entrepreneurs is seen as beneficial to the long-term viability of family firms, as shown by these results. According to conventional wisdom, these companies are doomed after the third generation due to a lack of qualified successors and a preference for employing based on personal connections rather than qualifications. The findings of this study show that family companies benefit from corporate entrepreneurship education.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The quality of the education provided by these management colleges and whether the M.B.A. graduates have gained the requisite skill set to be marketable in the job market are of paramount importance to all stakeholders. There have been stories of M.B.A. graduates having difficulty finding work in the global labor market. As a result, improving the quality of higher education is a top priority. Because of this, it is necessary to conduct a student satisfaction survey for NBA-accredited students in Tamil Nadu.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To investigate the impact of the **industrial revolution** on the growth of management education in India.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Only M.B.A. programs and management institutions affiliated with Tamil Nadu state universities were examined. The present study does not address other management institutions, such as I.I.M.s, private universities, and PGDM colleges, which provide a variety of management degrees. Relevance is significant, and the study's findings will significantly benefit management organizations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A qualitative research design is employed in this study. Academic specialists provided the critical data for this study. This study relied on secondary data. Secondary sources included academic journals, theses, magazines, and other periodicals.

EVOLUTION OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION

Over the last few decades, management education has grown at an unprecedented rate on a global and national scale. It is widely accepted that management education began in the United States in the late 19th century and quickly extended to Europe and Australia. Japan was the first Asian country to provide formal management education to the region. Thus, management education began in the United States before spreading to other parts of the world.

THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE GROWTH OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION

The industrial revolution in Western countries has had a significant impact on the rise of management education. There is now a greater demand for management skills to oversee the expanding industrial and economic activity. India's prosperity has fueled growth in demand for managers in both public and private sector units since the 1950s and increased globalization and liberalization. As a result, as the industrial revolution and globalization progressed, the demand for management education grew.

FACTORS CAUSING CHANGES IN MANAGEMENT EDUCATION IN INDIA

There is a shift taking place in the Indian management education environment. One of the most important causes of this new trend is that the competition in business is becoming more and more intense, as is the demand for skilled workers in the industry, as a change in the corporate and industrial landscape, as well as the involvement of government agencies in management education. As a result of these cases, India's management education has seen certain adjustments.

MANAGEMENT EDUCATION AND THE INSTITUTIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE IN INDIA

Indian business education is constructed on the foundation of institutional infrastructure. AICTE awards the M.B.A. equivalent of the PGDM program to a small number of institutions based on merit, including the Indian Institutes of Management (I.I.M.s), Departments of Universities, and Non-University Autonomous Institutions (NUIs), and Institutions Offering Management Courses via Distance Learning via Correspondence. Management education in India has been based on these institutions.

To maintain a competitive edge in the global economy, India's management education will need to be given more focus if it becomes a worldwide economic power.

SIGNIFICANT ISSUES IN MANAGEMENT EDUCATION IN INDIA

In India, management education deals with several critical challenges. It is necessary to ensure the quality of faculty, develop course material that is relevant to Indian conditions, promote research, develop an accreditation system, implement corporate governance for B-schools, provide student testing services, bring specialization, broaden the scope of perspective, teach real business issues, and instill a global mindset, to name just a few of the many tasks that need to be completed to achieve this goal.

EMPLOYMENT POTENTIALS OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION IN INDIA

As the state's industrial activity has grown, so have career opportunities for those with a degree in management. Managers will be in even greater demand as the pace of globalization and liberalization picks up. There is ample room for the B-schools to increase enrollment and match the increased demand for M.B.A.s in the expanding corporate sector. A larger student body is required, which can only be accomplished by increasing admissions.

The B-schools have a narrow spectrum of expertise. As a result, it is necessary to broaden the scope of specialty to encompass new fields such as entrepreneurial development and health care. To create fresh opportunities in business management, specializations must be sufficiently varied. Because of this, specialization must be simplified.

Perceptions of Deans/Directors of B-schools

The results show that the respondent Deans/Directors have a strong understanding of the expanding significance of economic sectors on a rapid growth trajectory. M.B.A.s could be qualified for a new job or entrepreneurship with their enhanced skill and knowledge if B-schools offered a wide range of subjects in their curricula, overcoming the restrictions of restricted specializations. As a result of these beliefs, modifications in specialties are likely required. Many Deans/Directors of B-schools cite salaries and perks as a significant H.R. issue. However, most respondents (36) believed it to be the second major issue in human resources. 7 and 18 respondents identified retaining and attracting personnel as the first and second most important H.R. issues, respectively. In comparison, 35 and 32 respondents regarded it as the second most crucial issue. Respondents placed human resources issues first and second, with 16 and 7 saying they had the most severe cases. Most 36 and 37-year-olds viewed them as H.R. issues of the second tier. Only two respondents ranked performance management as the most pressing issue in H.R., while most of the other 29 said it was the third most pressing issue. As a result of these and other considerations, we can conclude that attracting and keeping highly qualified professors is a significant challenge. Training for business school students in soft skills Management education should be incorporated into the plan of business schools. Communication, leadership, and conversational language are examples of soft skills that may be taught. Students who graduate from business schools are

more marketable because of these talents. Business schools and corporations must work together to offer students the resources they need to complete their project work. In this situation, the business school should devise a well-thought-out approach.

MANAGEMENT EDUCATION TO BE REVAMPED FOR INDUCTING SKILLS IN DECISION MAKING

When B-school graduates enter the workforce, they must bring the skills to make sound business decisions. When it comes to running a successful business, good decision-making skills are essential.

The management education system must be overhauled entirely to ensure that B-school graduates have the communication skills needed to succeed in the corporate world.

FOCUS ON MANAGEMENT SKILLS OF B-SCHOOL STUDENTS

For B-school graduates to live up to the high standards set by corporations, future management education strategies should emphasize this critical part of managerial ability.

There is a lot of competition and complexity in today's global corporate climate. As a business manager, you need to be fluent in the intricacies of modern international trade. Management education is required here. According to many companies surveyed, the management education system falls short of what companies need to comprehend business in a global setting. This void must be filled with the proper measures. Corporate business requirements must be considered in the future development of management education to meet global business in today's competitive climate. To address the needs of corporations, creative and inventive M.B.A.s are required. For the most part, business leaders who took part in a survey said that they felt that current management education did not adequately match their demands. Therefore, the future of management education should be geared toward producing creative and inventive M.B.A.s to suit the business community's needs. Management education needs a new strategy and approach to teaching M.B.A.s to take risks. This character attribute is critical in the face of today's worldwide environment's challenges.

ENHANCING THE EMPLOYABILITY OF MBAs

Future management education strategies should incorporate more input into management education to improve B-school graduates' employability. This is based on the comments from both B-school Deans/Directors and Corporates.

There is no coincidence of view when it comes to making it necessary for the industry to support B-school students conducting project work.

The faculty at business schools must help students improve the quality of their project work. Management education's future approach must be focused on this.

SIGNIFICANCE OF DECISION-MAKING SKILLS FOR MBAS

The ability to make decisions is a critical management skill for graduates. As a result, the future of management education should be based on teaching students how to make decisions.

According to Deans, Directors, and corporations, B-school students' lack of communication skills is a sign of the inadequacy of current management education. Future management education should focus on teaching students how to communicate effectively.

Differences in opinions between B-school directors and their companies suggest a lack of focus on problem-solving skills in management education. The future of management education should focus on developing problem-solving skills in B-school graduates.

CONCLUSION

The researcher concluded that, based on the findings of the study, the opinions of corporate executives and academic leaders, as well as his observations, there is a genuine desire to foster a cordial and healthy relationship between industry and academia to improve management education and better prepare students to meet the ever-changing needs and knowledge requirements of corporations in the twenty-first century. Learning management systems, online courses, live projects, and an emphasis on social responsibility at educational institutions are urgently required.

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